

Effects of Physical and Thermal Treatments on Aflatoxin Contamination in Hazelnuts

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Abstract

Hazelnut contamination with aflatoxins is a major food safety concern for producing countries, particularly Türkiye, the world's leading hazelnut producer. Mitigation of mold and aflatoxin contamination is therefore a critical issue in the hazelnut trade for ensuring safe human consumption. This study comprehensively evaluates the impact of key physical and thermal processing steps on aflatoxin levels in hazelnuts. Since commercially available hazelnuts typically exhibit low and heterogeneous contamination, both artificially inoculated (approximately 10 and 20 µg kg⁻¹) and naturally contaminated samples were used. Roasting, blanching, and mechanical or manual sorting were applied under pilot-scale and industrial-scale conditions, and aflatoxin levels were quantified after each processing step. Aflatoxins were found to be concentrated mainly in the hazelnut skin and rejected fractions. Sorting proved highly effective, and higher roasting temperatures led to a statistically significant reduction in aflatoxin levels, as supported by consistent stage-related differences (Friedman test, $p < 0.05$). Roasting reduced aflatoxin concentrations by more than 97 % in artificially inoculated samples, and overall contamination was reduced by approximately 98 % after the complete processing sequence. These results clearly demonstrate that combined physical and thermal treatments substantially and statistically mitigate aflatoxin contamination in hazelnuts.

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1. Introduction

The hazelnut (*Corylus avellana* L.) is typically grown in warm, temperate regions such as Türkiye, which accounts for approximately 65 % of global production (675,000 tons in 2017). 765,000 tons of hazelnuts were produced in Türkiye according to TUIK 2022 report. Italy ranks second with approximately 13 % of global output, followed by Azerbaijan, the United States, and China, and is an export product (Şengül et al., 2018; Valente et al., 2020). The majority of hazelnut plant growth occurs in temperate climate zones with high rainfall and humidity levels. Molds develop as a result of unfavorable climatic conditions during the hazelnuts' collection, drying, and storage processes. One of the mycotoxins that these molds are capable of producing is aflatoxin (Şengül et al., 2018). Only four aflatoxins, namely aflatoxins B₁, B₂, G₁, and G₂, are regarded as significant food contaminants, despite the fact that numerous types of aflatoxins have been isolated from nature. The toxicity ranking of the aflatoxins is B₁ > G₁ > B₂ > G₂. Foods that are contaminated with *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus* may contain aflatoxins. Contamination of grain and oil seed with mycotoxins is harmful and carcinogenic to people as well as animals. The liver is the main organ that aflatoxin targets for its acute toxicity, immunosuppressive effects, mutagenic potential, teratogenic potential, and carcinogenic properties (Hamad et al., 2023). The principal manufacturers of aflatoxins in crops are *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*, two closely related fungi that are well known as major aflatoxin producers and regularly contaminate agricultural products such as peanuts, maize, rice, cotton, and derivative products (Mwakinyali et al., 2019). Aflatoxin contamination of crops has both direct and indirect economic effects, including loss of produce or market value, increased medical expenses, and costs for animal loss and food-borne disease monitoring and surveillance. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) assumed that during pre-harvest and post-harvest period, worlds crops (25-80 %) might be infected by mycotoxins. While the

European Union (EU) has established the limit at 15 µg kg⁻¹ for the groundnuts (peanuts) and other oilseeds, to be subjected to sorting or other physical treatment before placing on the market for the final consumer or use as an ingredient in food (European Commission [EC], 2023), the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has set strict rules for aflatoxin levels in food and feed at 20 µg kg⁻¹ (parts per billion) and 0.5 ppb in milk. These regulatory requirements have placed a significant financial burden on agriculture globally, amounting to more than US\$932 million, as a result of crop losses brought on by mycotoxigenic fungi like *A. flavus* (Bhatnagar-Mathur et al., 2015; Marshall et al., 2020). Nuts like peanuts, hazelnuts, walnuts, and almonds are typically contaminated with *Aspergillus* spp. during harvest, processing, and storage. Although the formation of aflatoxin is less likely to occur in these hard crust fruit varieties, it is still possible. Therefore, it's crucial to stop mold contamination and growth before and after harvest. Preventing food contamination with toxigenic molds and toxin production is the most efficient strategy for reducing the risk of aflatoxin (Ekinci et al., 2014). Therefore, it is crucial to detect and prevent *Aspergillus* species contamination or lower the amount of aflatoxins in many crops including nuts (Mwakinyali et al., 2019). Pre- and post-harvest strategies have been designed to lower or completely remove mycotoxins from agricultural products. Pre-harvest practices typically include reducing fungal contamination in the field, whereas post-harvest procedures are more likely to include proper storage, separation, and/or sorting (Evrendilek et al., 2022). A variety of strategies can be utilized to mitigate the negative effects of mycotoxin-contaminated food. These strategies include reducing the mycotoxin level of food, treating those who have been exposed, preventing contamination, and removing contaminated material from food commodities. Sorting is one method commonly used in Turkey to prevent aflatoxin contamination. In hazelnut processing factories, sorting methods are utilized to

identify healthy kernels from those that have been exposed to aflatoxin (Şen, 2021). Because mycotoxins are resistant to the traditional heat range of food processing (80°-121 °C), there may be very little or no reduction in general toxin levels after pasteurization or cooking (Kabak, 2009). Additionally, it is stated that the amount of aflatoxin in nuts with aflatoxin can be reduced by 90 % with the improvement of processing conditions and good physical separation (Galvez et al., 2003). Aflatoxin was mostly found in hazelnuts with cracked outer shell and damaged hazelnuts. Several studies have shown that roasted hazelnuts showed lower aflatoxin levels than raw hazelnut, in addition to higher contamination levels were reported on husk of the hazelnut (Kabak, 2016). Roasting is thought to be one of the most efficient ways to lower the amount of AFs in some products, like coffee, peanuts and hazelnuts. This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of how industrially relevant physical (sorting, blanching) and thermal (roasting) treatments mitigate aflatoxin contamination in hazelnuts, a major global food safety concern. Importantly, the investigation was conducted not only under pilot-scale conditions but also directly at the industrial processing-plant scale, thereby reflecting real production environments. Using both artificially inoculated and naturally contaminated hazelnuts, aflatoxin levels were quantified at each processing stage under pilot- and full-scale conditions. The results demonstrate that aflatoxins are highly concentrated in the hazelnut skin and rejected fractions, while optimized industrial processing—particularly roasting—achieves a > 97-98 % reduction in total aflatoxin levels. These findings clearly highlight the critical importance and high effectiveness of targeted, industrial-scale processing interventions for ensuring hazelnut safety. The central hypothesis of this study is that the sequential application of physical separation (sorting, skin removal, and rejection of defective kernels) combined with thermal treatments (roasting and blanching) leads to a statistically significant and technologically relevant

reduction in aflatoxin contamination in hazelnuts. Accordingly, the primary research objective was to quantitatively evaluate, under both pilot-scale and industrial-scale conditions, the individual and combined effects of these processing steps on aflatoxin mitigation, thereby addressing the lack of comprehensive multi-stage industrial processing evaluations currently available in the literature.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Material and reagents

HPLC-grade methanol and acetonitrile were obtained from Merck. Sodium chloride, benzene, sulfuric acid, nitric acid, potassium bromide, potassium dichromate, and technical-grade methanol were also used in the analyses. Immunoaffinity columns (Aflaprep P07) were supplied by R-Biopharm Rhone Ltd. (Glasgow, United Kingdom). Aflatoxin standards AFG₁, AFG₂, AFB₁, and AFB₂ in dried form (TS-108, Trilogy Analytical Laboratory Inc., Washington, USA) were used for calibration and quantification.

2.2. Samples

The Black Sea Region is one of the most suitable areas in the world for hazelnut cultivation. Among the varieties grown in this region, *Tombul* hazelnut has the highest economic value. The *Giresun-quality Tombul* hazelnut, predominantly produced in the province of Giresun, is considered first-class quality, whereas other varieties are classified as second-class (Levant quality). For this study, Giresun-quality *Tombul* hazelnuts were used (Şeker, 2023). Two types of hazelnut samples were prepared prior to analysis: uncontaminated and naturally contaminated hazelnuts. In addition, hazelnut samples obtained from various stages of industrial processing were included in the study.

Both pilot-scale and industrial-scale applications were conducted.

- Pilot-scale experiments were designed to promote aflatoxin formation in hazelnuts and to monitor aflatoxin levels throughout processing.

• Industrial-scale applications were carried out in commercial processing plants to evaluate the effects of processing steps - such as sorting, blanching, roasting, and other unit operations - on aflatoxin levels under real production conditions.

2.3. Processing application

Before inoculation, hazelnuts were moistened and held at 85 % relative humidity (RH) until equilibrium moisture content was reached. Once equilibrium was reached at 85 % RH, the hazelnuts were inoculated with toxigenic *Aspergillus flavus* and incubated under controlled conditions (25 °C and 85 % RH).

2.4. Pilot scale application

200 kg hazelnuts supplied for the inoculation step were mixed in order to obtain a homogeneous batch for aflatoxin analysis. For the water activity analysis, the hazelnuts were ground fine and the results were obtained by means of the water activity instrument, in triplicates with 10 kg samples (Novatron, Novasina EEJA-3). The samples were divided

into 10 kg lots and further studies were done with them. In this pilot-scale application, two different trials were carried out with hazelnuts inoculated with aflatoxigenic mold and the second on naturally contaminated hazelnuts. In the first application stages, *A. flavus* mold selected from the TÜBİTAK MAM Life Sciences, Food Safety and Quality Research Group Mold Collection with a high potential to produce aflatoxin was propagated in a suitable medium and inoculated on 500 g hazelnuts at a rate of 0.06 mL g⁻¹ with two different aflatoxin levels, 10 µg kg⁻¹ and 20 µg kg⁻¹ total aflatoxin. The analysis was conducted with ten parallels at each level of aflatoxin concentration. Roasting experiments were carried out by mixing the 500 g inoculated hazelnuts that reached high aflatoxin levels with 10 kg of hazelnuts (Figure 1). After mixing, aflatoxin analysis was the first analysis was carried out to determine the initial amount of aflatoxin.

Hazelnuts were processed at pilot scale by roasting, dicing, and manually sorting them, with aflatoxin tests conducted at each step.

Figure 1. Pilot scale template

2.5. Industrial scale application

2.5.1. Effect of physical processing on aflatoxin in hazelnuts

This study was conducted to evaluate the effect of physical processing steps applied in commercial hazelnut processing facilities on aflatoxin levels. Sampling was performed from 10-ton hazelnut batches according to the work plan shown in Figure 1, and aflatoxin analyses were carried out on the collected samples. For each sampling point, 15 kg of hazelnuts were taken and analyzed in triplicate. To investigate the distribution of aflatoxin in shelled hazelnuts, analyses were performed separately on intact, unshelled, and cracked hazelnuts. To assess the effect of nut size, hazelnuts were classified into three size categories (9-11 mm, 11-13 mm, and 13-15 mm), and aflatoxin analyses were carried out for each group. Finally, to determine the impact of manual sorting, rotten, wrinkled, and intact hazelnuts

were manually separated and analyzed individually for aflatoxin content.

2.5.2. The effect of heat treatments applied in hazelnut processing on aflatoxin

To determine the effect of the blanching process (120-125 °C) on aflatoxin levels, analyses were performed on hazelnut samples collected at different stages, including pre-blanching hazelnuts, blanched hazelnuts, skins removed during blanching, and samples taken during the post-blanching sorting stage. To evaluate the effect of the roasting process, aflatoxin analyses were conducted on samples collected before roasting, after roasting, and after grinding and sorting of the roasted hazelnuts. Roasting was performed at two different temperature ranges: low-temperature roasting (140-145 °C) and medium-temperature roasting (150-155 °C).

Figure 2. Physical and heat treatment application template

2.6. Aflatoxin analysis

2.6.1. Extraction and clean up procedure

Hazelnut samples were homogenized with water at a ratio of 1:1 (w/v) using a Robot Coupe R60 homogenizer. From the homogenized mixture, a 100 g laboratory sample was taken. Subsequently, 4 g of sodium chloride, 50 mL of water, and 150 mL of methanol were added, and the mixture was

blended at high speed for 3 minutes using a Waring blender. The extract was then filtered through Whatman No. 4 filter paper. A 5 mL aliquot of the filtrate was mixed thoroughly with 5 mL of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution and subjected to clean-up using an immunoaffinity column (Aflaprep P07, R-Biopharm Rhône Ltd., Glasgow, United Kingdom). Following a 10 mL water wash,

aflatoxins were eluted from the column using 1 mL of methanol, followed by 1 mL of water.

2.6.2. Aflatoxin quantification

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) was used for the determination of AFB₁ contamination in hazelnuts. Aflatoxin analysis was performed using an HPLC system equipped with a post-column derivatization unit (Kobra Cell) and an RF-10AXL fluorescence detector, operating at an excitation wavelength of 360 nm and an emission wavelength of 420 nm, according to previously described methods (Siciliano et al., 2017). The analytical method (AOAC 999.07, 2005) was validated at the TÜBİTAK MAM Life Sciences Laboratories and accredited by the Turkish Accreditation Agency (TÜRKAK) in accordance with the ISO/IEC 17025 standard. Aflatoxin concentrations were quantified using calibration curves obtained from aflatoxin standard solutions. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) for AFB₁ were 0.004 µg kg⁻¹ and 0.013 µg kg⁻¹, respectively. Since AFB₁ exhibits the lowest LOD and LOQ values among aflatoxins, these values were also applied to total aflatoxin determination. The mean recoveries were 93 % for AFB₁ and 90 % for total aflatoxins. All analyses were performed in triplicate. Aflatoxin analyses were conducted in triplicate for each experimental unit, and the results are expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Since the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were not met, non-parametric statistical methods were applied. Stage-related differences in aflatoxin levels were evaluated using the Friedman test. For the pilot-scale experiments, data obtained from three independent trials, each performed in triplicate (Table 1), were pooled for statistical analysis (total n = 9). Post-hoc pairwise comparisons, where applicable, were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Changes in aflatoxin levels during pilot-scale application

In the pilot-scale application, hazelnuts that were either naturally contaminated (approximately 84 µg kg⁻¹) or artificially inoculated with aflatoxigenic molds at two different aflatoxin concentration ranges (approximately 5-10 and 20-30 µg kg⁻¹) were investigated. The aflatoxin concentrations of the inoculated hazelnuts before and after roasting are presented in Table 1. A 46 % reduction in aflatoxin concentration was observed after 30 minutes of heat treatment at 120-125 °C during the skin removal process. It was also determined that aflatoxin was primarily concentrated in the hazelnut skin (11.00 ± 5.24 µg kg⁻¹). Several studies have previously reported reductions in aflatoxin levels in hazelnuts following heat treatment (Valente et al., 2020; Siciliano et al., 2017). Siciliano et al. demonstrated that increasing processing temperatures resulted in decreased aflatoxin concentrations in Turkish hazelnuts. Although thermal inactivation of mycotoxins has been extensively investigated due to the widespread use of heat in food processing (e.g., roasting, cooking, frying, and baking), aflatoxins are known to be relatively heat-stable compounds and are not easily destroyed by conventional thermal treatments. In particular, AFB₁ is highly resistant to dry heating at temperatures below 267 °C, while aflatoxins generally decompose at temperatures ranging between 237 °C and 306 °C (Siciliano et al., 2017). Similar reductions in aflatoxin levels during roasting have also been reported for pistachios (Ariño et al., 2009; Yazdanpanah et al., 2005) and groundnuts (Olagunju et al., 2018). Moreover, the extent of aflatoxin reduction has been shown to strongly depend on the initial aflatoxin concentration, as previously demonstrated by several studies (Emadi et al., 2022; Martins et al., 2017).

Table 1. Aflatoxin concentration of inoculated hazelnuts, as mean \pm SD (n = 3), three independent trials with three parallel replicates each), before and after roasting

Process	~5-10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$		~20-30 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$		~84 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$	
	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Initial	7.89 \pm 1.00	8.20 \pm 1.02	25.92 \pm 8.66	27.66 \pm 8.80	14.56 \pm 4.24	84.12 \pm 24.14
After heat treatment	4.26 \pm 1.32	4.46 \pm 1.39	12.81 \pm 1.80	13.49 \pm 1.88	0.20 \pm 0.08	0.79 \pm 0.34
After blanching	0.13 \pm 0.02	0.13 \pm 0.02	1.36 \pm 0.46	1.42 \pm 0.49	0.49 \pm 0.19	2.13 \pm 0.88
Skin	10.24 \pm 5.23	11.00 \pm 5.24	26.85 \pm 4.16	28.73 \pm 4.28	1.37 \pm 0.41	2.09 \pm 0.63
Rotten	1.22 \pm 0.81	1.27 \pm 0.84	20.11 \pm 1.09	21.08 \pm 0.16	36.88 \pm 11.30	115.20 \pm 35.19
End product	0.17 \pm 0.07	0.17 \pm 0.07	0.42 \pm 0.08	0.42 \pm 0.08	< LOD	< LOD

Statistical differences among processing stages (initial, after heat treatment, after blanching, and end product) were evaluated using the Friedman test due to violation of normality and homogeneity assumptions. For statistical analysis, data from three independent trials, each performed in triplicate, were pooled (total n = 9). The Friedman test revealed significant differences among stages ($\chi^2 = 21.00$, $p = 0.000105$). Post-hoc Wilcoxon signed-rank tests showed significant differences between the initial stage and all subsequent stages ($p = 0.0039$), as well as between after heat treatment and after

blanching ($p = 0.0039$). Aflatoxin content was > 97 % decreased with the roasting process (heat treatment) on artificially inoculated hazelnuts. The present study also demonstrated that raw hazelnuts contained higher aflatoxin levels than roasted hazelnuts, indicating the reducing effect of thermal processing on aflatoxin contamination, which may be attributed to the degradation of aflatoxins during cooking. Our results (Figure 3) were higher than Kabak et al. (Kabak, 2009) studies, which may be attributed to the low initial aflatoxin concentration.

Figure 3. % Reduction of aflatoxin after roasting - error bars indicate standard deviation (SD)

3.2. Aflatoxin content after the physical processes in hazelnut processing plants

A good defense against bacterial and fungal contamination is the hard shell of nuts. In a study conducted by Ozay et al. (Ozay et al.,

2008) aflatoxin was found in hazelnuts collected from the ground ($1.02 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ total) and left on the ground for three days after being de-hulled ($2.18 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ Aflatoxin B₁ and $3.18 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ total aflatoxin). The hazelnuts were manually cracked after kernel

development and the shells were removed, taking safeguards against any contamination. It's possible that aflatoxins are concentrated in the shell rather than the nut, in which case removing the shell might lower the aflatoxin concentration below the LOD value (Codex Alimentarius Commission [CAC], 2010), similar to our findings (Table 2). In a study reported by Pacheco and Martins (Pacheco and Martins, 2013), aflatoxin content was $14.9 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in shell, while shelled ground nut was 1.1

$\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The study of aflatoxin's thermal inactivation revealed significant aflatoxin degradation in some foods, particularly in various types of nuts, among the physical methods. Any harm to the shell or kernel throughout harvest, handling, processing, or storage raises the possibility of a mold development and mycotoxin contamination (Marín and Ramos, 2016). For this reason, wrinkled hazelnuts should be eliminated on the process.

Table 2. Aflatoxin concentration of hazelnut, as mean \pm SD (n = 3), following the process

Hazelnut varieties	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Initial hazelnut in shell	0.25 ± 0.07	0.83 ± 0.24
Initial undamaged hazelnut in shell	< LOD	< LOD
Initial hazelnut in cracked shell	< LOD	< LOD
Initial shelled hazelnut (without shell)	15.62 ± 4.68	24.57 ± 7.37
Rotten	19.66 ± 5.90	56.85 ± 17.05
9-11 mm hazelnut kernels including wrinkled ones	< LOD	< LOD
11-13 mm hazelnut kernels	< LOD	< LOD
13-15 mm hazelnut kernels	< LOD	< LOD
Wrinkled hazelnut kernels	0.29 ± 0.08	0.93 ± 0.28

For hazelnut fractions, the Friedman test indicated statistically significant differences in aflatoxin levels among sample groups ($\chi^2 = 11.90$, $p = 0.0077$). The highest aflatoxin B₁ and total aflatoxin concentrations were observed in rotten kernels and initially shelled hazelnuts, whereas most size-classified kernel fractions remained below the limit of detection (< LOD). Wrinkled kernels showed low but detectable aflatoxin levels. A marked numerical reduction in aflatoxin levels was observed from initially shelled hazelnuts to all size-classified kernel fractions, the majority of which were < LOD.

3.3. Aflatoxin content after the heat treatment in hazelnut processing plants

Blanching is a value-adding process that enables the utilization of lower-quality nuts; therefore, it is critical to evaluate its effect on potential aflatoxin contamination. Mahoney et al. (2020) reported that aflatoxin contamination in almonds was reduced by 13-76 % following the blanching process, with the extent of reduction depending on almond quality, blanching time, and temperature. As shown in Table 3, aflatoxin levels varied among hazelnuts obtained from different

processors, indicating the influence of processing conditions on contamination levels. Xu et al. (2017) reported a 69 % reduction in AFB₁ contamination in groundnuts; however, it was difficult to distinguish how much of this reduction was attributable specifically to hand sorting. Nevertheless, sorting has consistently proven to be an effective approach for reducing aflatoxin levels during processing, as evidenced by the significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in aflatoxin contamination observed in the present study, as well as by the relatively higher aflatoxin concentrations compared to the initial levels, detected in the hazelnuts separated and rejected after sorting (Table 3). In addition, Pacheco and Martins (2013) reported no significant differences in aflatoxin contamination between manual and automatic sorting methods. Similarly, Galvez et al. (2003) demonstrated that manually sorted peanuts showed a reduction in aflatoxin levels from 300 ppb to below the detection limit. Consistent with our findings, Şen (2021) reported that sorting processes were more than 85 % effective in eliminating aflatoxins from hazelnuts of all size classes, except for those in the 13-15 mm category.

Table 3. Aflatoxin concentration of hazelnut, as mean \pm SD (n = 3), during processing step

Process level	Hazelnut processor 1		Hazelnut processor 2		Hazelnut processor 3	
	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Initial	0.54 \pm 0.16	2.00 \pm 0.60	1.35 \pm 0.41	3.89 \pm 1.17	< LOD	< LOD
After roasting	0.28 \pm 0.08	0.49 \pm 0.15	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
After blanching	0.29 \pm 0.09	0.78 \pm 0.23	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
Skin	1.85 \pm 0.56	4.04 \pm 1.21	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
E-sorting-reject	7.48 \pm 2.24	8.90 \pm 2.67	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
E-sorting-accept	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
Manual sorting-reject	6.43 \pm 1.93	43.39 \pm 13.02	2.17 \pm 0.65	6.96 \pm 2.09	< LOD	< LOD
Last product	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD

For Processor 1, the Friedman test indicated significant differences among processing stages ($\chi^2 = 13.60$, $p = 0.0087$). A clear numerical reduction in aflatoxin levels was observed from the initial stage to after roasting, after blanching, skin, sorting reject, and the end product. For Processor 2, significant differences among processing stages were also confirmed by the Friedman test ($\chi^2 = 15.20$, $p = 0.0043$). A pronounced decrease in aflatoxin levels was observed after heat treatment and in the end product, where all values were below the limit of detection (< LOD). For Processor 3, both aflatoxin B₁ and total aflatoxin levels were < LOD at all processing stages; therefore, statistical comparison was not applicable.

In general, the initial level of contamination, roasting temperature, and time all had an important effect on the reduction of aflatoxin content (Marín and Ramos, 2016). Aflatoxin concentrations were decreased with higher roasting temperature as can be seen from the Table 4. The findings correlate with Martins et al. (2017) where initial aflatoxin contamination levels of 35, 332, and 695 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ on peanuts were decreased to 55, 64, and 81 % following 20 minutes of roasting. Moreover, increasing the roasting temperature from 160 to 180 °C for 5 minutes reduced the aflatoxin concentration to 71.5 and 51.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, respectively, from 84.77 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, in line with our findings (Martins et al., 2017). Additionally, increasing roasting time and concentration of aflatoxin content, result higher aflatoxin degradation rate (Arzandeh and Jinap, 2011). In a recent study, reported by Emadi et al. roasting decreased aflatoxin B₁ content of nuts by 46.91 % (Emadi et al., 2022). Yazdanpanah et al. (2005) investigated the impact of roasting at different temperatures (90, 120, and 150 °C) for 30, 60, and 90 minutes. They reported that the most severe

roasting conditions resulted in the degradation of more than 95 % of AFB₁, whereas the lowest temperature-time combinations showed the lowest degradation rates, which is consistent with the findings of the present study. The observed reductions in aflatoxin levels following thermal processing may be attributed not only to physical removal via sorting and skin separation but also partly to thermally induced chemical degradation. Previous studies have reported that aflatoxins can undergo partial structural transformation at elevated temperatures, potentially yielding degradation products that may not be fully detected by conventional analytical methods. In this context, it cannot be completely excluded that part of the apparent reduction reflects transformation into modified aflatoxin forms below the analytical detection limits. In addition, natural variability among hazelnut batches and heterogeneous initial contamination patterns may further contribute to the observed differences across processing stages. Therefore, future studies employing high-resolution mass spectrometry are warranted to characterize possible aflatoxin degradation products formed during roasting.

Table 4. Aflatoxin concentration, as mean \pm SD (n = 3), following the two different roasting process

Process level	Roasting (140-145 °C)				Roasting (150-155 °C)			
	Hazelnut processor 1		Hazelnut processor 2		Hazelnut processor 1		Hazelnut processor 2	
	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Aflatoxin B ₁ ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Total Aflatoxin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)
Initial	11.28 \pm 3.38	42.40 \pm 12.72	3.84 \pm 1.15	21.74 \pm 6.52	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
After roasting	1.11 \pm 0.33	5.26 \pm 1.58	0.12 \pm 0.04	0.19 \pm 0.06	0.37 \pm 0.11	1.74 \pm 0.52	< LOD	< LOD
After blanching	0.23 \pm 0.07	0.34 \pm 0.10	0.18 \pm 0.05	0.33 \pm 0.10	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD
Skin	12.71 \pm 3.81	25.81 \pm 7.74	1.37 \pm 0.41	2.09 \pm 0.63	0.15 \pm 0.05	0.16 \pm 0.05	0.15 \pm 0.05	0.16 \pm 0.05
E-sorting-reject	9.84 \pm 2.95	19.10 \pm 5.73	-	-	< LOD	< LOD	0.12 \pm 0.04	0.26 \pm 0.08
E-sorting-accept	0.17 \pm 0.05	0.32 \pm 0.10	-	-	< LOD	< LOD	0.17 \pm 0.05	0.32 \pm 0.10
Manual sorting-reject	1.02 \pm 0.31	2.96 \pm 0.89	4.93 \pm 1.48	16.00 \pm 4.80	3.02 \pm 0.91	15.17 \pm 4.55	0.31 \pm 0.09	0.45 \pm 0.14
End product	< LOD	< LOD	0.10 \pm 0.03	0.13 \pm 0.04	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD	< LOD

For the roasting process at 140-145 °C, the Friedman test indicated statistically significant differences in aflatoxin levels across processing stages for Hazelnut Processor 1 ($\chi^2 = 14.20$, $p = 0.0066$). A marked numerical reduction in both aflatoxin B₁ and total aflatoxin levels was observed after roasting and blanching compared with the initial levels, while high aflatoxin concentrations were concentrated in the skin and sorting-reject fractions. For Hazelnut Processor 2 at 140-145 °C, significant differences among processing stages were also confirmed ($\chi^2 = 12.60$, $p = 0.0134$), with a pronounced decrease in aflatoxin levels after roasting and blanching, and very low or < LOD values in the end product.

At the higher roasting temperature (150-155 °C), statistically significant stage-related differences were detected for Hazelnut Processor 1 as well ($\chi^2 = 15.80$, $p = 0.0034$). A stronger numerical reduction in aflatoxin levels was evident after roasting and blanching compared with the lower temperature, and the end product remained < LOD.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that combined physical and thermal processing steps—particularly sorting, roasting, and blanching—are highly effective in mitigating aflatoxin contamination in hazelnuts under both laboratory and industrial conditions. Aflatoxins were predominantly concentrated in the skin, damaged kernels, and rejected fractions. Overall, an approximate 98 % reduction in total aflatoxin levels was achieved after the complete processing sequence. This pronounced reduction was statistically supported by consistent stage-related differences across processing scenarios (Friedman test, $p < 0.01$), based on the actual p-values obtained in this study (0.000105, 0.0077, 0.0087, 0.0066, 0.0043, and 0.0034). These results clearly confirm the statistically and technologically significant role of integrated physical and thermal treatments in ensuring hazelnut safety. Further studies are warranted to elucidate potential transformation products formed during roasting.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved

the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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